

ISic3003

I.Sicily inscription 3003

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

marble (Luna)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 571

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. M(arcus) Antonius Callistus

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Marcus Antonius Callistus

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493965

EDR 138379

EDCS 22200383

Bibliography

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 9

Ferrara, F. 1829. Storia di Catania sino alla fine del secolo xviii. Catania. At 393 no.2

Manganaro, G. 1961. Ricerche di epigrafia siceliota. I. Per la storia del culto delle divinita orientali in Sicilia. *Siculorum Gymnasium*. 14: 175-198. At 184 no.2 ph

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3003. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4357064>